

Sectoral interactions and primary drivers in integrated CLEWs modelling: Insights from Kenya

Authors

Roberto Heredia-Fonseca^{*1}, Pietro Lubello², Francesco Gardumi¹, Will Usher¹

¹ Department of Energy Technology – Energy Systems, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm 114 28, Sweden

² UCL Energy Institute, University College London, London WC1H 0NN, United Kingdom

Supplemental Tables

Input parameters used in the GSA

The following tables contain information on input parameters used in the GSA. The column "name" is the name of the parameter from OSeMOSYS¹. The column "group" is the name given to grouped parameters.

Table S 1. Demands, energy service demands, crops, and water demands.

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
Accumulated AnnualDemand	acc_ckg	RE1,CKGURB	11.8	11.8	28	40	2-6
		RE1,CKGRUR	30.4	30.4	32	46	
	acc_dem_crp	RE1,CRPWHE	2365.1	2365.1	1890	2840	5,7
		RE1,CRPMAI	4188.8	4188.8	3350	5030	
		RE1,CRPBRL	86	86	65	105	
		RE1,CRPCOF	44.5	44.5	35	55	
		RE1,CRPTEA	458.9	458.9	365	555	
		RE1,DEMSUG	899.5	899.5	715	1080	
	acc_dem_sec	RE1,CRPPHB	763	763	610	920	8,9a
		RE1,DEMICM	25.33	25.33	70	120	
		RE1,DEMIFP	0.52	0.52	3.47	5.2	
		RE1,DEMIOI	30.78	30.78	90	140	
		RE1,DEMTAI	0.46	0.46	1.65	2.5	
		RE1,DEMTRB	0.55	0.55	1.24	1.9	
		RE1,DEMTRC	17.6	17.6	60	100	
		RE1,DEMTRH	4.57	4.57	10	30	
		RE1,DEMTRL	4.55	4.55	10	30	
		RE1,DEMTRM	14.45	14.45	10	30	
	RE1,DEMTWD	0.09	0.09	0.32	0.5		
	RE1,DEMTRR	1.99	1.99	7.18	10.8		
acc_dem_wpr	RE1,WODPRO	5108	5108	6560	9840	10	
acc_dem_wtr	RE1,PUBWATIND	0.303	0.303	0.43	0.54	11	
acc_dem_wtr	RE1,PUBWATMUN	0.495	0.495	1.4	1.67		

Note. ^a varied \pm 20% by 2050.

Table S 2. Specified annual demands. Demands linked to a specific use time during the year, such as electricity.

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
Specified AnnualDemand	ssp_dem_sec	RE1,DEMCCO	4.89	4.89	10	30	8,9,12a
		RE1,DEMRC1	0.88	0.88	2.78	4.2	
		RE1,DEMRC2	0.11	0.11	0.29	0.4	
		RE1,DEMRL1	4.54	4.54	10	30	
		RE1,DEMRL2	1.41	1.41	3.69	5.5	
		RE1,DEMRO1	3.08	3.08	9.71	14.6	
		RE1,DEMRO2	0.99	0.99	2.58	3.9	

Note. ^a. varied \pm 20% by 2050.

Table S 3. Capital Costs power supply technologies

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
CapitalCost	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRBIO001	2000	3000	2000	3000	13
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRCOA001	1970	2970	1970	2970	13,14
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRDIST	2000	3000	2000	3000	13
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO001	3320	3320	2650	3990	13,14
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO002	3470	3470	2770	4170	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO003	3430	3430	2740	4120	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO004	3430	3430	2740	4120	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO005	3590	3590	2870	4310	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO006	3800	3800	3040	4560	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRGEO007	3800	3800	3040	4560	
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRHFO001	1610	1610	1280	1940	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRHYD001	3430	3430	2740	4120	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRHYD002	3460	3460	2760	4160	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRHYD003	3430	3430	2740	4120	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRHYD004	3220	3220	2570	3870	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRHYD005	3480	3480	2780	4180	
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRLFO001	990	1490	990	1490	
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRNGS001	680	1020	680	1020	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRSOL001	1220	1220	610	920	
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRTRN	280	440	280	440	13
	cc_pwr	RE1,PWRURN001	2300	3460	2300	3460	13,14
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND001	1580	1580	940	1350	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND002	1740	1740	1040	1480	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND003	1620	1620	970	1380	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND004	1580	1580	940	1350	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND005	1650	1650	990	1410	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND006	1550	1550	930	1320	

	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND007	1790	1790	1070	1530	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND008	1920	1920	1150	1640	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND009	1700	1700	1020	1450	
	cc_pwr_ren	RE1,PWRWND010	1670	1670	1000	1420	

Table S 4. Capital Costs stove-cooking sector

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
CapitalCost	cc_ckg	RE1,CKGELCurb	134	403	134	403	15,16
		RE1,CKGLPGurb	69	208	69	208	
		RE1,CKGKERurb	2	7	2	7	
		RE1,CKGGASurb	481	1444	481	1444	
		RE1,CKGWODurb	37	111	37	111	
		RE1,CKGCHCurb	2	7	2	7	
		RE1,CKGOTHurb	16	48	16	48	
		RE1,CKGELCrur	182	547	182	547	
		RE1,CKGLPGrur	50	151	50	151	
		RE1,CKGKERrur	3	9	3	9	
		RE1,CKGGASrur	481	1444	481	1444	
		RE1,CKGWODrur	85	255	85	255	
		RE1,CKGCHCrur	1	5	1	5	
		RE1,CKGOTHrur	4	13	4	13	
		RE1,CKGICSrur	4	13	4	13	
		RE1,CKGICSurb	16	48	16	48	
		RE1,CKGICSchurb	18	54	18	54	
RE1,CKGICSchrur	17	51	17	51			

Table S 5. Discount rate global (dr) and hurdle rates (dr_tech)

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
DiscountRate	dr	RE1	0.08	0.12	0.08	0.12	17
Discount RateI dv	dr_tch	RE1,PWRCOA001	0.11	0.149	0.11	0.149	18
		RE1,PWRHFO001	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.09	
		RE1,PWRLFO001	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.09	
		RE1,PWRNGS001	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.09	
		RE1,PWRURN001	0.09	0.13	0.09	0.13	
	dr_tch_ren	RE1,PWRBIO001	0.11	0.149	0.11	0.149	18
		RE1,PWRGEO001	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
		RE1,PWRGEO002	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
		RE1,PWRGEO003	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
		RE1,PWRGEO004	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
		RE1,PWRGEO005	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
		RE1,PWRGEO006	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12	
	RE1,PWRGEO007	0.089	0.12	0.089	0.12		

		RE1,PWRHYD001	0.068	0.1	0.068	0.1	
		RE1,PWRHYD002	0.068	0.1	0.068	0.1	
		RE1,PWRHYD003	0.068	0.1	0.068	0.1	
		RE1,PWRHYD004	0.068	0.1	0.068	0.1	
		RE1,PWRHYD005	0.068	0.1	0.068	0.1	
		RE1,PWRSOL001	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.09	
		RE1,PWRWND001	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND002	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND003	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND004	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND005	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND006	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND007	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND008	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND009	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	
		RE1,PWRWND010	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1	

Note. Individual/hurdle rates are only applied to electricity generation technologies.

Table S 6. Emission penalty and crop parameters: evapotranspiration (crp_evt), yields (yld_crp)

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
Emissions Penalty	pm_pty	RE1,PM25	0	0	134.4	230.4	19,20
		RE1,PM25 _{fur}	0	0	112	192	
Output ActivityRatio	crp_evt	RE1,LNDWHEHI,WTREVT,1	0.14	0.398	0.14	0.398	21
		RE1,LNDWHEHR,WTREVT,1	0.321	0.413	0.321	0.413	
		RE1,LNDMAIHI,WTREVT,1	0.569	0.853	0.569	0.853	
		RE1,LNDMAIHR,WTREVT,1	0.488	0.732	0.488	0.732	
		RE1,LNDBRLHI,WTREVT,1	0.216	0.341	0.216	0.341	
		RE1,LNDBRLHR,WTREVT,1	0.295	0.351	0.295	0.351	
		RE1,LNDCOFHI,WTREVT,1	0.215	0.486	0.215	0.486	
		RE1,LNDCOFHR,WTREVT,1	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.8	
		RE1,LNDTEAHI,WTREVT,1	0.451	0.696	0.451	0.696	
		RE1,LNDTEAHR,WTREVT,1	0.5	0.893	0.5	0.893	
		RE1,LNDSUCHI,WTREVT,1	0.32	0.577	0.32	0.577	
		RE1,LNDSUCHR,WTREVT,1	0.32	0.577	0.32	0.577	
		RE1,LNDPHBHI,WTREVT,1	0.305	0.457	0.305	0.457	
		RE1,LNDPHBHR,WTREVT,1	0.305	0.457	0.305	0.457	
	RE1,LNDOTHCRP,WTREVT,1	0.51	0.766	0.51	0.766		
	yld_crp	RE1,LNDWHEHI,CRPWHE,1	520	650	520	650	5,21,22
		RE1,LNDWHEHR,CRPWHE,1	450	630	450	630	
		RE1,LNDMAIHI,CRPMAI,1	850	920	850	920	
RE1,LNDMAIHR,CRPMAI,1		610	750	610	750		
RE1,LNDBRLHI,CRPBRL,1		610	630	610	630		
RE1,LNDBRLHR,CRPBRL,1		550	620	550	620		

		RE1,LNDCOFHI,CRPCOF,1	180	240	180	240	
		RE1,LNDCOFHR,CRPCOF,1	160	200	160	200	
		RE1,LNDTEAHI,CRPTEA,1	260	280	260	280	
		RE1,LNDTEAHR,CRPTEA,1	230	250	230	250	
		RE1,LNDSUCHI,CRPSUC,1	9000	9500	9000	9500	
		RE1,LNDSUCHR,CRPSUC,1	7300	9400	7300	9400	
		RE1,LNDPHBHI,CRPPHB,1	300	350	300	350	
		RE1,LNDPHBHR,CRPPHB,1	200	325	200	325	

Table S 7. Built land and other crops (Ind_blt_othcrp), Cost inputs for crops (vc_crp), and fuel/commodity prices (vc_fuel)

name	group	indexes	min_value base_year	max_value base_year	min_value end_year	max_value end_year	Ref
Total Technology AnnualActivity LowerLimit	Ind_blt_othcrp	RE1,LNDBLT	9.29	9.29	7	15	21
		RE1,LNDOTHCRP	17	17	13	25	
VariableCost	vc_crp ^a	RE1,IMPWHE,1	0.21	0.316	0.21	0.316	5,23- 25
		RE1,LNDWHEHI,1	34	50	34	50	26,27
		RE1,LNDWHEHR,1	34	50	34	50	
		RE1,IMPMAI,1	0.186	0.278	0.186	0.278	5,23- 25
		RE1,LNDMAIHI,1	56	84	56	84	28
		RE1,LNDMAIHR,1	56	84	56	84	
		RE1,LNDMAILI,1	37	55	37	55	
		RE1,LNDBRLHI,1	106	159	106	159	27
		RE1,LNDBRLHR,1	106	159	106	159	
		RE1,LNDCOFHI,1	293	439	293	439	29,30
		RE1,LNDCOFHR,1	153	229	153	229	
		RE1,LNDTEAHI,1	177	266	177	266	31,32
		RE1,LNDTEAHR,1	161	242	161	242	
		RE1,IMPSUC,1	0.422	0.633	0.422	0.633	5,23- 25
		RE1,LNDSUCHI,1	334	502	334	502	33
		RE1,LNDSUCHR,1	307	460	307	460	
		RE1,IMPPHB,1	0.578	0.868	0.578	0.868	34
		RE1,LNDPHBHI,1	57	86	57	86	35
	RE1,LNDPHBHR,1	38	57	38	57		
	vc_fuel ^a	RE1,IMPGAS,1	0.3	0.46	0.3	0.46	8,12,36
		RE1,FTEAGRDSL,1	34	51	34	51	
		RE1,FTEINDDSL,1	34	51	34	51	
		RE1,FTETRADSL,1	34	51	34	51	
RE1,IMPBIO,1		1.41	2.11	1.41	2.11		
RE1,IMPCOA,1		2.02	3.02	2.02	3.02		
RE1,IMPELC001,1		14.44	21.67	14.44	21.67		

		RE1,IMPELC002,1	22.22	33.33	22.22	33.33	
		RE1,IMPGSL,1	21.44	32.16	21.44	32.16	37,38
		RE1,IMPKER,1	20.64	30.96	20.64	30.96	
		RE1,IMPJFL,1	21.44	32.16	21.44	32.16	
		RE1,IMPLPG,1	27.6	41.4	27.6	41.4	
		RE1,IMPLFOELD,1	20.64	30.96	20.64	30.96	8,12,36
		RE1,IMPHFOMOM,1	4.5	6.76	4.5	6.76	
		RE1,IMPHFONAI,1	5.44	8.16	5.44	8.16	
		RE1,IMPURN,1	1.04	1.56	1.04	1.56	39
		RE1,IMPNGS,1	1.6	2.4	1.6	2.4	37,38

Note. ^a varied \pm 20% by 2050.

Supplemental references

1. Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., Hughes, A., Silveira, S., DeCarolis, J., Bazillian, M., et al. (2011). OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development. *Energy Policy* 39, 5850–5870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2011.06.033>.
2. Nerini, F.F., Ray, C., and Boulkaid, Y. (2017). The cost of cooking a meal. The case of Nyeri County, Kenya. *Environmental Research Letters* 12, 065007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/AA6FD0>.
3. United Nations (2022). *World Population Prospects: The 2022 Revision*.
4. Munene F. M. (2003). *Household Population and Housing Characteristics*.
5. KNBS (2022). *Economic Survey 2022*.
6. KNBS (2019). *Population by County and Sub-County. Kenya Population and Housing Census I*.
7. UN (2022). United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2022). *World Population Prospects 2022*.
8. Pye, S., Akute, M., and Lubello, P. (2024). OSeMOSYS Kenya WESM - Demand workbook. Preprint at Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425582> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425582>.
9. Lubello, P., Akute, M., and Pye, S. (2024). OSeMOSYS Kenya WESM - Documentation. Preprint at Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425600> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425600>.
10. Cheboiwo, J. (2016). *Private forestry sector in Kenya: status and potential*.
11. FAO (2024). *AQUASTAT - Dissemination system -water*.
12. Kihara, M., Lubello, P., Millot, A., Akute, M., Kilonzi, J., Kitili, M., Mukuri, F., Kinyanjui, B., Hoseinpoori, P., Hawkes, A., et al. (2024). Mid- to long-term capacity planning for a reliable power system in Kenya. *Energy Strategy Reviews* 52, 101312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESR.2024.101312>.
13. KenGen GDC, KETRACO, Ministry of Energy, EPRA, Kenya Power, KETRACO, REREC, and NuPEA (2022). *Updated Least Cost Power Development Plan, Study Period: 2022-2041*.
14. NREL (2024). *2024 Annual Technology Baseline. National Renewable Energy Laboratory Golden, CO*.
15. Ministry of Energy (2019). *Kenya Household Cooking Sector Study: Assessment of the Supply and Demand of Cooking Solutions at the Household Level*.
16. Jeuland, M., Tan Soo, J.S., and Shindell, D. (2018). The need for policies to reduce the costs of cleaner cooking in low income settings: Implications from systematic analysis of costs and benefits. *Energy Policy* 121, 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2018.06.031>.
17. National Parameters <http://kenya.cri-world.com/index.php?r=tradable%2Flist-parameters>.

18. Department of Energy and Climate Change (2015). Electricity Generation Costs and Hurdle Rates Lot 1: Hurdle Rates update for Generation Technologies.
19. Larsen, B. (2015). Benefits and Costs of the Air Pollution Targets for the Post-2015 Development Agenda. Copenhagen Consensus Center.
20. Fann, N., Baker, K.R., and Fulcher, C.M. (2012). Characterizing the PM2.5-related health benefits of emission reductions for 17 industrial, area and mobile emission sectors across the U.S. *Environ Int* 49, 141–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVINT.2012.08.017>.
21. Fischer, G., Nachtergaele, F.O., van Velthuizen, H.T., Chiozza, F., Franceschini, G., Henry, M., Muchoney, D., and Tramberend, S. (2021). Global agro-ecological zone V4 – Model documentation (FAO) <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb4744en>.
22. OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2018-2027 Special focus: Middle East and North Africa - World | ReliefWeb <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/oecd-fao-agricultural-outlook-2018-2027-special-focus-middle-east-and-north-africa>.
23. of Goa, G. (2021). Economic Survey 2020-21. Directorate of Planning, Statistics & Evaluation Porvorim-Goa.
24. KNBS (2011). Economic Survey 2011.
25. KNBS (2015). Economic Survey 2015.
26. Kamwaga, J., Macharia, G., Boyd, L., Chiurugwi, T., Midgley, I., Canales, C., Marcheselli, M., and Maina, I. (2016). Kenya wheat production handbook 2016. *Exp Agric* 37.
27. Jones, D. (2024). Determining The Cost Of Production Of Cereals (Maize, Wheat & Barley) - Cropnuts. <https://cropnuts.com/farm-cost-of-production-cereals-maize-wheat-barley/>.
28. Egerton University (2017). Cost of Maize Across Different Systems and Regions in Kenya: Implications for Food Security and Pricing. Tegemeo Institute of Agricultural Policy and Development.
29. Muriithi, L. Viability of Coffee Farming as a Business. KALRO.
30. Snyder, M., and Gitona, K. (2022). Coffee Annual. Unites States Department of Agriculture Foreign Agricultural Service (USDA).
31. CPDA (2008). Report on small-scale Tea sector in Kenya. Christian Partners Development Agency.
32. KTDA (2019). Annual Report and Financial Statements. Kenya Tea Development Agency.
33. SafiOrganics (2023). Sugarcane Farming in Kenya. <https://safiorganics.co.ke/blog/sugarcane-farming-in-kenya/>.
34. Mathayo, G. (2023). A Look At The Prices Of Various Beans Varieties In Kenya. <https://sokodirectory.com/2023/03/a-look-at-the-prices-of-various-beans-varieties-in-kenya/>.
35. Katungi, E.M., Karanja, D., Wozemba, D., Mutuoki, T., and Rubyogo, J.-C. (2011). A cost-benefit analysis of farmer based seed production for common bean in Kenya. Preprint at African Crop Science Society.

36. Lubello, P., Akute, M., and Pye, S. (2024). OSeMOSYS Kenya WESM. Preprint at Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425489> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425489>.
37. EPRA (2023). Maximum Retail Petroleum Prices in Kenya. <https://www.epra.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/EPRA-Fuel-Price-Press-Release-May-2023.pdf>.
38. EPRA (2020). Energy and Petroleum Statistics Report 2020. Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority.
39. World Nuclear Association (2023). Economics of Nuclear Power. <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/economic-aspects/economics-of-nuclear-power>.